

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO TEACHING SPEAKING SKILLS

Scientific supervisor: **Karimova Nilufar**

Nozima Makhmudova Otabek kizi

1st year student of the Uzbekistan State University of World Languages

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15178846>

Abstract: *This article explores innovative approaches to teaching speaking skills, focusing on various methods such as communicative language teaching, task-based learning, and the use of technology to enhance fluency and confidence. The article also highlights the role of games and pronunciation training in improving speaking skills. It also discusses the challenges faced by students and provides recommendations for effective speaking instruction.*

Keywords: *Communicative language teaching, task-based learning, fluency, pronunciation, speaking proficiency, innovative teaching methods, technology in language learning.*

Speaking is one of the most important skills in language learning while old methods are gradually becoming insufficient in speaking, the need for new methods and techniques is increasing. In this regard, modern methods are one of the ways that can help develop more than old ones, and through which it is possible to improve speaking skills quickly and easily.

Several problems arise in the process of learning to speak, and finding solutions to them is considered very important. Among these, the speaker's low self-confidence in the speaking process, the lack of frequent and real communication, and knowledge in grammar and mainly problems with pronunciation are obstacles.

Communicative language learning as an innovative approach

The communicative method serves not only for the exchange of information in social communication but also for the implementation of education and upbringing, the intellectual development of the individual and increasing motivation to study. This method helps to develop students' speaking skills by creating a natural and effective environment in the process of language learning. Before using the communicative method to improve speaking skills, it is important to study how this approach is interpreted in the methodology of teaching foreign languages and analyze the opinions of scientists on this issue. Researchers have studied various aspects of this method and come to important conclusions about its effectiveness. The research of these scholars helps to understand how the communicative method affects the development of speaking skills, increases students' self-confidence, and generally

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

makes the language learning process more effective. Through this method, students can not only increase their speech activity, but also reduce their speech errors, strengthen their grammatical knowledge, and acquire the skills to communicate freely in real life.

Utilizing technology to enhance fluency and confidence, in particular digital tools and Internet resources, play an important role in learning foreign languages, including speaking skills. These tools increase students' interest, encourage them to think freely, independently and logically, and also prepare them for oral communication. In addition, modern technologies help teachers to conduct lessons in an interactive and interesting way. For example, the use of games such as debates, conversations and competitions develops students' free, independent and logical thinking, and prepares them for oral communication. At the same time, the use of technological tools requires students to be familiar with and able to use information and communication technologies. This further enriches their general knowledge and skills.

Interactive games are an effective tool for developing speaking skills.

1. *Role-playing*: Students take on different roles in different situations, which allows them to prepare for real-life communication.

2. *Debates*: Students defend their opinions on a given topic, which improves their critical thinking and argumentation skills.

3. *Storytelling*: Students create and present stories individually or in groups, which develops their creativity and fluency.

4. *Q&A games*: Students ask and answer questions to each other, which improves their quick thinking and communication skills.

5. *"Who am I?" game*: Students write the name of a famous person or object in their head and try to find it by asking questions. This game develops questioning and description skills. These games help students develop their speaking skills and make lessons more interesting.

Training pronunciation plays a very important role in developing speaking skills. Correct pronunciation not only ensures correct understanding of words, but also increases the effectiveness of communication. Mistakes in pronunciation can lead to misunderstandings.

Pronunciation development methods:

XORIJIY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

▪Phonetic exercises: These exercises help improve pronunciation. For example, exercises such as pronouncing individual sounds correctly and separating words into syllables.

▪Listening and repetition: Students can improve their pronunciation by listening to texts and repeating them. This method also develops their hearing skills.

▪Games and interactive activities: Practicing pronunciation through games increases students' interest and encourages them to actively participate.

▪Using audio and video materials: Listening to native speakers and imitating them is an effective way to improve pronunciation. An individual approach to teaching pronunciation is also important, as each student's needs and difficulties may be different.

In conclusion, speaking is one of the most important skills in language learning, and innovative approaches to its development are of great importance. This article reviews the effectiveness of modern language teaching methods, including communicative language learning, task-based learning, the use of technology, games, and pronunciation exercises. In the process of developing speaking skills, several problems arise, such as students' lack of self-confidence, lack of real communication, and difficulties with pronunciation. Interactive methods, technological tools, and task-based teaching methods can be used to solve these problems. Also, the role of games and interactive exercises in improving speaking skills is very important, as they allow students to speak freely in a natural environment. Pronunciation exercises help students form correct pronunciation and intonation. Therefore, the use of innovative approaches in language teaching is an important factor in increasing students' confidence in speaking, developing their communication skills, and achieving effective results. In the future, further improvement and wider implementation of these methods in practice may serve to increase the effectiveness of language teaching.

References:

1. <https://interscience.uz>
2. https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/xorijiy-tillarni-o-qitishda-raqamli-texnologiyalarning-ahamiyati?utm_source
3. https://www.intereuroconf.com/index.php/MSRAIDP/article/download/1597/1308?utm_source
4. https://moluch.ru/archive/308/69404/?utm_source
5. https://journalsnuu.uz/index.php/1/article/download/1404/592?utm_source
6. <https://ilmiy.bmti.uz>
7. https://tsuull.uz/sites/default/files/maqola_munavvara_qurbonova.pdf?utm_source